

Optically Active *s*-Triazines: Part V

Preparation of L(+) or L(-)- α -(2-Arylamino-4-Alkylamino-*s*-Triazin-6-Yl-Amino)-Glutaric Acids

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Optically active L (+) or L (-)- α -(2-Arylamino-4-alkylamino-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-glutaric acids have been prepared by condensing 2-arylamino-4, 6-dichloro-*s*-triazines, first with L (+)-glutamic acid at 40° to 45° and then with alkylamines like methyl, ethyl and butylamine. The optical rotations have been taken in pyridine as well as in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (0.25N).

S-TRIAZINE nucleus has been the subject of several investigators in the realm of potential therapeutic agents for diseases due to bacteria and protozoa¹, sleeping sickness^{2,3}, malaria^{4,5}, cancer^{6,7}, and possess antiviral⁸ property. We have prepared L (+)- or L (-)- α -(2-arylamino-4-alkylamino-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-glutaric acid of type (I) in order to study optical activity.

where R = aryl, R' = chloro or alkylamino.

The compounds were prepared by condensing 2-arylamino-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine^{5,9-11} (1 mole), first with L (+)-glutamic acid [α]_D²⁰ = +32, 1N hydrochloric acid (1 mole) as sodium salt at 40°-45° and then with different alkylamines like methyl, ethyl and butylamine (1 mole) using dioxane as solvent at 80°-90°. 2-Arylamino-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazines were prepared by condensing cyanuric chloride (1 mole) with different bases (1 mole) like aniline, substituted aniline and α -naphthylamine. The optical rotations were taken in pyridine as well as in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (0.25N).

In case of L (-)- α -(2-anilino-4-chloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-glutaric acid, the introduction of substituent in benzene ring at para position increases the optical activity in pyridine while it is less in ortho and meta derivatives. The optical activity is of the order of para > meta > ortho. The substitution of chloro by methylamino group decreases the optical activity.

The specific rotations of ethylamine derivatives are greater than methyl and butylamine which may be due to steric hindrance and hydrogen bonding. Such regularities are not observed in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (Table 2).

Experimental

a) Preparation of 2-arylamino-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazines:

Cyanuric chloride (0.025 mole) was dissolved in dioxane or acetone and kept at 0°. To it, arylamine (0.025 mole) was added with constant stirring (1 hr) and aqueous sodium hydroxide (0.025 mole) was added to neutralise the acid evolved and products obtained were isolated.

b) Preparation of L (-)- α -(2-arylamino-4-chloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-glutaric acids:

2-Arylamino-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (0.001 mole) was dissolved in dioxane (20 ml.) and solution of glutamic acid (α)_D²⁰ = +32, 1N hydrochloric acid (0.001 mole) in aqueous sodium hydroxide (5.0 ml, 4%) was added. The temperature of the reaction mixture was raised to 40°-45° and kept stirred for 2 hr. Contents were diluted with ice-water, acidified (congo-red) and the products were isolated (Physical constants are recorded in Table 1).

c) Preparation of L (-) or L (+)- α -(2-arylamino-4-alkylamino-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-glutaric acids:

L (-)- α -(2-arylamino-4-chloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl-amino)-glutaric acid (0.001 mole) was treated with aqueous sodium hydroxide (2.5 ml., 4%) and dissolved in dioxane (10 ml.). The solution of alkylamine (0.001 mole) was added and refluxed for 2 hr at 80°-90° followed by the addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide (2.5 ml., 4%) to neutralise the acid evolved. Contents were diluted with ice-water and acidified (congo-red). The product obtained were insoluble

TABLE I—OPTICALLY ACTIVE *s*-TRIAZINES OF TYPE—I

Sr. No.	R	R'	Molecular formula	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Nitrogen	
						Found	Calculated
1.	Phenyl	chloro	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ N ₅ O ₄ Cl	33.6	187-88	19.8	19.76
2.	Phenyl	methylamino	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₆ O ₄	90.0	178-80	26.3	26.59
3.	Phenyl	ethylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄	85.9	200-02	23.00	23.33
4.	Phenyl	butylamino	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₄	57.6	97-97	21.4	21.65
5.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	chloro	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ Cl	45.1	230-32	19.3	19.18
6.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	methylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄	22.4	255-56	23.5	23.33
7.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	ethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄	29.4	250-51	22.6	22.46
8.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	butylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄	27.3	275-75	20.9	20.89
9.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	chloro	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ Cl	78.3	185-87	19.25	19.18
10.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	methylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄	71.2	204-05	23.10	23.33
11.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	ethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄	83.2	215-17	22.6	22.46
12.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	butylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄	47.4	167-68	20.85	20.89
13.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	chloro	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ Cl	87.4	210-12	20.3	19.18
14.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	methylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄	61.0	195-97	23.6	23.33
15.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	ethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄	58.7	222-24	22.5	22.46
16.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	butylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄	27.3	178-79	20.65	20.89
17.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	chloro	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	32.5	215-17	18.45	18.38
18.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	methylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅	36.6	213-15	22.20	22.35
19.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	ethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₅	39.2	215-16	21.6	21.54
20.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	butylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₅	18.3	212-14	20.1	20.09
21.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	chloro	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	51.3	201-02	18.20	18.38
22.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	methylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅	81.3	235-36	22.60	22.35
23.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	ethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₅	73.5	220-22	21.45	21.54
24.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	butylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₅	73.1	221-23	20.3	20.09
25.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	chloro	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₅ Cl	28.8	202-04	18.40	18.38
26.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	methylamino	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₅	61.0	190-92	22.40	22.35
27.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	ethylamino	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₅	54.9	208-09	21.45	21.54
28.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	butylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₅	36.6	165-67	20.00	20.09
29.	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl	chloro	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ Cl	92.7	190-92	18.00	18.13
30.	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl	methylamino	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₄ Cl	57.9	177-80	22.00	22.11
31.	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl	ethylamino	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₄ Cl	58.2	215-16	21.5	21.32
32.	<i>m</i> -chlorophenyl	butylamino	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₆ O ₄ Cl	79.6	168-70	19.6	19.91
33.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	chloro	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄ Cl ₂	78.3	185-86	18.3	18.13
34.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	methyamino	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₄ Cl	55.9	245-47	22.3	22.11
35.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	ethylamino	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₆ O ₄ Cl	51.4	238-40	21.25	21.32
36.	<i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	butylamino	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₆ O ₄ Cl	50.3	203-04	20.00	19.91
37.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	chloro	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₆ O ₆ Cl	58.0	195-96	21.4	21.20
38.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	methylamino	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₆	71.0	204-06	24.9	25.06
39.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	ethylamino	C ₁₆ H ₁₉ N ₇ O ₆	78.4	170-71	24.3	24.19
40.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	butylamino	C ₁₈ H ₂₃ N ₇ O ₆	82.5	228-30	22.7	22.63
41.	α -Naphthyl	chloro	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₅ O ₄ Cl	87.2	228-29	17.5	17.46
42.	α -Naphthyl	methylamino	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₄	30.5	185-87	22.4	21.21
43.	α -Naphthyl	ethylamino	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₆ O ₄	34.3	190-92	20.50	20.48
44.	α -Naphthyl	butylamino	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ N ₆ O ₄	50.5	171-72	19.20	19.18

TABLE 2—SPECIFIC ROTATION OF L(+) OR L(-) α (2-ARYL- AMINO-4-CHLORO)ALKYLAMINO-*s*-TRIAZIN-6-YL-AMINO)-GLUTARIC ACID

Sr. No.	Aryl	R' = Chloro				R' = Methylamino				R' = Ethylamino				R' = Butylamino			
		Pyridine		NaOH		Pyridine		NaOH		Pyridine		NaOH		Pyridine		NaOH	
		$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$	$(1,1)$ C	$[\alpha]_D^{30}$
1.	Phenyl	0.99	-25.3	1.03	-9.7	0.60	-8.3	0.50	+10.0	0.65	-61.6	0.47	+10.6	0.32	-12.5	0.35	+12.5
2.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	0.42	-11.9	0.92	+9.8	0.40	+10.0	0.63	+15.9	0.33	+15.2	0.81	+24.7	0.41	+12.2	0.87	+23.0
3.	<i>m</i> -Tolyl	1.30	-23.1	0.85	-5.9	0.74	-18.9	0.88	+18.2	0.71	-126.8	0.88	+6.8	0.66	-15.2	0.89	+5.6
4.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	1.09	-27.5	0.96	-10.4	0.67	-19.4	0.94	+10.6	0.72	-27.7	1.14	+11.4	0.20	-20.0	0.65	+9.2
5.	<i>o</i> -Anisyl	1.30	-15.4	1.00	-5.0	0.83	-14.5	0.83	+12.0	0.73	-26.0	0.84	+5.9	0.28	-14.3	0.71	+5.6
6.	<i>m</i> -Anisyl	1.05	-19.9	0.76	-6.6	0.48	-75.0	0.99	+5.1	0.38	-42.1	0.72	+5.5	0.38	-44.7	0.81	+4.9
7.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	1.17	-34.2	0.97	-5.2	0.50	-20.0	0.40	+12.5	0.52	-80.8	0.38	+10.5	0.31	-32.2	0.40	+10.0
8.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	0.85	-23.5	1.07	-4.7	0.73	-16.4	0.90	+11.1	0.70	-18.0	0.91	+15.4	0.74	-6.8	0.95	+5.3
9.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	1.16	-30.2	0.78	-12.8	0.79	-19.0	0.112	+8.9	0.72	-138.0	0.99	+5.1	0.75	-16.0	0.97	+5.2
10.	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	0.57	-43.9	0.52	-73.5	0.62	-16.1	0.92	-10.9	0.40	-50.0	1.05	-13.6	0.55	-18.2	1.00	-10.0
11.	α -Naphthyl	1.12	-13.4	0.58	-8.6	0.63	-11.1	0.72	+7.1	0.60	-41.7	0.69	+5.8	0.66	-15.2	0.73	+6.8

in benzene, chloroform, acetone but sparingly soluble in alcohol and pyridine. They were crystallised from alcohol (Physical constants are recorded in Table 1).

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